

Effect of Industrial Democracy Practices on Employees Performance, A Case Study of Manufacturing Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

¹Ujoatu, Ezinne Peace, ² Emerole, O.B.

^{1,2}Department of Industrial Relations and Personnel Management
Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia state
e-mail:nchetapexzy@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

*This paper examined the effect of industrial democracy practices on employee's performance, a study of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically the study ascertained the effect of workers participation in decision making on employee turnover rate in the manufacturing firms in Enugu and determined the effect of collective bargaining on employee retention in the manufacturing firms in Enugu. The study employed both primary and secondary data in achieving its objectives. The sample size of the study is 120 which was determined using Taro Yamane's formula. A total of 120 Questionnaires were administered to 120 respondents and 95 were received back, representing 79.17% response rate. The study found that worker's participation in decision-making have a significant effect on the employees turnover rate in the manufacturing firm in Enugu $t = 6.831^{***}$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Result also show that there is a significant relationship between collective bargaining and employee retention in manufacturing firms in Enugu state ($r = 0.279^{**}$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Based on the findings it is recommended that a democratic management style should be imbibed in for manufacturing firms in Enugu State.*

Key words: Industrial democracy, employee participation, sample size, employee performance

1.0 INTRODUCTION

People who are satisfied with their jobs exhibit commitment towards the organizational goals and objectives and show inclination to engage themselves to deliver their fullest abilities and adhere to policies and ideology of organizations Allen and Snyderman (2018). Motivating People and making them satisfied, committed and engaged in this modern era of increasing interests, increasing global competition and soaring technology is not an easy task. Making employees to take part in decision-making is proven to make them feel important, satisfied and committed to the employee performance Armstrong (2018). Several management experts and authors pointed that involving employees in all organizational decisions is the solution to deal with the situation Avwokim(2014). However, employee involvement or participation appears to be only a scheme or a platform to motivate them to some extent Baridan(2017). There are several aspects to be taken care such as employee job satisfaction and employee job responsibility. There should be financial reward to improve employee performance Armstrong (2018).

A poor approach towards industrial democracy on the part of manager could create ill feelings resulting into dissatisfied employees, employee withholding performance and low moral resulting in low productivity that could be costly to the organization Asika (2021). Most Nigerian organizations are faced with problems such as career development, training, skilled manpower, low productivity, job dissatisfaction and other challenges facing human resources managers in managing their employee performance in order to achieve organizational goals for improving employee performance. These problems are directly related with one another Certo (2020).

Cummings (2017), the objective for the quest for enhance productivity by-business organizations is to improve the welfare of its employees through providing satisfaction of their needs, what economist call utility Cooper(2020). However, the absence of literature on whether the effect of industrial democracy on employee performance in manufacturing firms in Enugu State creates a difference in employee satisfaction, employee job responsibility, and the level of employee performance constitute a gap to be filled by the paper. Therefore, this paper aimed at examining the effect of Industrial democracy on the employees' performance on manufacturing firms in Enugu State.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Employee performance

Employee performance is defined as the way to perform the job tasks according to the prescribed job description Dobb, (2020). Performance is the art to complete the task within the defined boundaries Ezejeje,(2020). There are lots of variables that affect the performance of the employee. These include managers attitude, organisational culture, personal problems and financial reward. The literature on employee performance clearly explains that employees who are satisfied; happy with their jobs have a stronger loyalty to doing a good job and look forward to improving the organizations' customer satisfaction and expectation. Employees who are satisfied have higher intentions of excellent performance with their organization, which results in a reduced turnover rate while employees who feel that co-workers behaviour is off-putting or rude often consider taking a job elsewhere Clegg (2019).

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHOD

3.1 Materials

A set of self- developed questionnaire and personal interviews were used in data collections. However the systematic sampling technique was used to select Ten (10) firms out of the forty-seven (47) manufacturing firms registered with Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) Enugu State branch. One hundred and twenty (120) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the twelve (12) selected firms (that is twelve copies for each of the firms). One hundred and ten (110) copies were returned. The grading system is shown in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Grading Schedule

CLASSIFICATION	GRADE	POINTS
Great extent	GE	5
Considerable extent	CE	4
Moderate extent	ME	3
Slight extent	SE	2
Not at all	NA	1

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

A total of 120 Questionnaires were administered to 120 respondents and 95 were received back, representing 79.17% response rate. The remaining 25 questionnaire was discarded because the questionnaires were not fully filled and answered. This ensured that the sample size as was

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originally designed remained almost the same thereby ensuring representativeness of the target population and validity of the result of the study as shown in Table 4.1 .

Table 4.1: Analysis of Questionnaire

Level	Distributed Questionnaire	% Distributed	Retrieved questionnaire	% retrieved	Questionnaire Not retrieved	% lost
Senior Staff	30	25.00	23	19.17	7	5.83
Middle Staff	55	45.83	41	34.17	14	11.67
Junior Staff	35	29.17	31	25.83	4	3.33
Total	120	100.00	95	79.17	25	20.83

Source: Field survey, 2022

4.1.1 Characteristics of Respondent

Table 4.2: Distribution of respondents based on sex

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	69	72.63
Female	26	27.37
Total	95	100

Source: Field survey questionnaire, 2022

Gender of the respondents is shown in Table 4.2 above. The analysis of their responses showed that 72.63% of the respondent were males while 27.37% were females. This means that there were more male in manufacturing Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. This means that the distribution is gender sensitive in favour of males. This could be attributed to the fact that men are more committed to petroleum related jobs (manufacturing) than the women who have less interest but are engaged in more administrative activities.

Table 4.3: Distribution of the respondents based on age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 25	21	22.11
25 – 34	33	34.74
Above 34	41	43.16
Total	95	100.00

Source: Field Survey questionnaire, 2022

Table 4.3 shows that 43.16% represented majority fall above 34 years, about 34.74% falls within 25-34, while 22.11% falls below 25 years respectively. This means that majority of the respondent are young, productive and vibrant. This represents an active stage in life. The implication of this age bracket on employee morale in an organization is increase in performance. These group of employees are “independent and enterprising thinkers who relish responsibility, demand immediate feedback, and expect a continuous sense of accomplishment.

“They are regarded as the drivers of organizational performance and therefore, they are essential to the growth of every organization.

Table 4.4: Distribution of the respondents based on marital status

Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	21	22.11
Married	74	77.89
Total	95	100

Source: Field survey questionnaire, 2022

Table 4.4 shows that 22.11% and 77.89% were single and married respectively. This reveals that the majority of the respondent were married. The implication is that there are more stable staff which are better positioned to improve organizational performance. This implied that a high proportion of respondents had family responsibilities and are stable. This stability create conducive environment for good citizen training, development of personal integrity, which are very important for efficient uses of resources in manufacturing firm.

Table 4.5: Distribution of respondents based on length of service

Length of service	Frequency	Percentage
1 - 5	18	18.95
6 – 10	11	11.58

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11 – 15	15	15.79
16 – 20	22	23.16
21 and above	29	30.53
Total	95	100.00

Source: Field survey questionnaire, 2022

Table 4.6 reveals that majority (30.53%) of the respondent have 21 and above length of service. It has been noted that workers would count more on their length of service for increased performance rather than educational attainment. The result has some positive implications on increased performance because the number of years a staff has spent in an organization may give an indication of the practical knowledge he has acquired on how he can overcome certain inherent job problems. This has significant implications for managing human resources, thereby increasing performance.

4.1.2 Effect of workers participation on employee turnover in the manufacturing firms in the selected organization

Research question one: Does workers participation in decision making has any effect on employee turnover in the manufacturing firms in the selected organization?

Table 4.6: Coded responses on effect of workers participation in decision making on employee turnover rate in the manufacturing firms in Enugu N = 95

S/N	Questions	GE	CE	ME	SE	NA	Total	Mean	Remark
1	The decisions in my department are made through consultation with members of the department and this have increase our turnover rate	44	35	10	6	0	402	4.23	Accepted
2	My supervisor encourages people to speak out when they disagree with decision	28	48	10	8	1	379	3.99	Accepted
3	My organization have suggestion box for taking suggestion on how to improve workplace environment safety	22	57	10	6	0	380	4.00	Accepted
4	I have an opportunity to say what has to be done on my job which increase our turnover rate	14	28	12	25	16	284	2.99	Rejected
5	Employee are allow to participate in decision making process in matters that relates to higher turnover rate in my organization	14	40	7	22	12	307	3.23	Accepted
6	Management and employee meets regularly to discuss issues of employee	12	23	19	11	30	261	2.75	Rejected

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	safety in workplace							
7	My supervisor encourages subordinates to participate in important decisions	14	57	22	2	0	368	3.87 Accepted
8	Management and employee meets regularly to discuss issues of employee safety in workplace	15	52	15	5	8	346	3.64 Accepted
9	I often offer suggestions to my supervisor to help solve work-related problems.	15	56	11	10	3	355	3.74 Accepted
10	In this organization, I have high degree of influence in organizational decisions.	11	49	20	12	3	338	3.56 Accepted
11	I often participate in decisions regarding my job.	15	36	11	21	12	306	3.22 Accepted
12	In this organization I can participate in setting new company policies.	11	30	15	11	28	270	2.84 Rejected
13	In this organization, my views have a real influence in company decisions.	8	31	20	19	17	279	2.94 Rejected
14	I have confidence in my ability to participate effectively.	13	45	22	14	1	340	3.58 Accepted
15	I feel good when I cooperate and	16	22	15	13	29	268	2.82 Rejected

recognized on issues concerning the organization.	
Clustered mean for decision rule:-	3.43 Accepted

Source: Field survey, 2022

From the result, fifteen questions were designed in the questionnaire to ascertain the effect of workers participation in decision making on employee turnover rate in the manufacturing firms in Enugu. From the result ten (10) of the variables in the table were accepted by the mean range used for decision which is 3.0 and above. This result shows that the mean responses for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 13 and 14 surpassed the criterion mean (3.52, 3.87, 4.23, 3.99, 4.00, 3.23, 3.87, 3.64, 3.74, 3.56, 3.22 and $3.58 \geq 3.0$). Specifically “The decisions in my department are made through consultation with members of the department and this have increase our turnover rate has on the average the highest mean ($\bar{X}= 4.23$) i.e. the respondents indicated strong agreement to the question statement; this was followed by “My organization have suggestion box for taking suggestion on how to improve workplace environment safety” has mean of ($\bar{X}= 4.00$); this was followed by “My supervisor encourages people to speak out when they disagree with decision.” ($\bar{X}=3.99$).

Others are shown on the table. Also from the table five items (4, 11, 12 and 15) were rejected since is less than 3.0, they include “I have an opportunity to say what has to be done on my job which increase our turnover rate, “Management and employee meets regularly to discuss issues of employee safety in workplace” “In this organization I can participate in setting new company

policies, “In this organization I can participate in setting new company policies” and “ I feel good when I cooperate and recognized on issues concerning the organization”.

Furthermore, the clustered mean was 3.43 which was accepted, this therefore implies that workers participation has effect in decision making on employee turnover rate in the manufacturing firms in Enugu. One of the strongest tools of participative management is employee involvement. In employee involvement system, every employee in the organization is given the opportunity to make recommendations in order to improve the organizational performance (Sarminah, 2011).

Research question two: What are the effect of collective bargaining on employee retention in the manufacturing firms in Enugu?

Table 4.7: Coded responses on what are the effect of collective bargaining on employee retention in the manufacturing firms in Enugu N = 95

S/N	Questions	GE	CE	ME	SE	NA	Total	Mean	Remark
		5	4	3	2	1			
16	Most key decisions on management labour matters in the manufacturing firms are made through collective bargaining.	25	5	29	30	6	298	3.14	Accepted
17	Through collective bargaining programmes measures that beep up the	13	45	22	14	1	340	3.58	Accepted

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	ability of employee to work have been executed.							
18	Through collective bargaining, productivity measures to enhance job productivity and employee retention has been established	47	29	11	6	2	398	4.19 Accepted
19	Issues that have enhanced the performance of manufacturing firms are adopted through collective negotiation by employee and management.	23	18	20	22	12	303	3.19 Accepted
20	Through collective bargaining, all staff of manufacturing firms has helped to ensure organizational peace.	15	56	11	10	3	355	3.74 Accepted
21	My Organization has through collective bargaining established procedure for settlement of complaint and grievances	12	23	19	11	30	261	2.75 Rejected
22	My Organization has through collective bargaining enhanced job productivity and	14	57	22	2	0	368	3.87 Accepted

organizational performance so as to retain their workers	
Clustered mean for decision rule:-	3.49 Accepted

Source: Field survey, 2022

From the result shown in Table 4.7 above six of the items in the table were accepted by the mean range used for decision which is 3.0 and above “Through collective bargaining, productivity measures to enhance job productivity and employee retention has been established” has on the average the highest mean ($\bar{X}= 4.19$) and was accepted i.e. the respondents indicated strong agreement to the question statement; followed by “My Organization has through collective bargaining enhanced job productivity and organizational performance so as to retain their workers ($X= 3.87$) while “My Organization has through collective bargaining established procedure for settlement of complaint and grievances” was rejected because their mean is less than 3.0.

Furthermore, the clustered mean was 3.49 which was accepted, the implication is that collective bargaining has effect on employee retention in the manufacturing firms in Enugu. In response to research question two, the respondents indicated that manufacturing firms in Enugu has used collective bargaining effectively to enhance organizational performance through employee retention. For instance, measures on how to enhance job productivity are adopted through collective bargaining and key decisions affecting labour management relations are adopted through collective bargaining.

4.2 DATA ANALYSIS

4.2.1 Hypothesis one

H₀₁: Worker’s participation in decision-making does not have any significant effect on the employees turnover rate in the manufacturing firm in Enugu. The hypothesis was tested using OLS regression as shown in Table 4.10.

Table 4.8: OLS estimate for test of hypothesis one

Dependent Variable: Employees

turnover rate

Method: Least Squares

Included observations: 95

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Worker’s participation	0.578874	0.084732	6.831837	0.0000
C	3.969342	0.228685	17.35724	0.0000
Mean dependent				
R-squared	0.334164	var		2.494737

Adjusted R-squared	0.327004	S.D. dependent var	0.897676
Akaike info			
S.E. of regression	0.736421	criticon	2.246798
Sum squared resid	50.43534	Schwarz criterion	2.300563
Hannan-Quinn			
Log likelihood	-104.7229	criticr.	2.268523
F-statistic	46.67399	Durbin-Watson stat	1.323133
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Eviews Output 2022

From the regression analysis above, the value of the R^2 is 0.334164, this suggest 33.41% of the changes in employees turnover rate is caused by the independent variables (Worker’s participation). The result shows that the coefficient of Worker’s participation was statistically significant in explaining the dependent variable.

The intercept β_0 (3.969342) shows the value of employees turnover rate when the values of the independent variable are indeterminate or when they are zero; this means that when the independent variable (Worker’s participation) is 3.969342.

F-Statistics

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The value of the F-stat, according to the result of the regression is given as (46.67399) 0.00000.
The decision rule for the F-stat is goodness of fit statistic is satisfactory

Hypotheses 1 which states that worker’s participation in decision-making does not have any significant effect on the employees’ turnover rate in the manufacturing firm in Enugu. On the specific, the co-efficient worker’s participation was significant at 1% and positively related to employees’ turnover rate, this implies that an increase in worker’s participation will increase the turnover rate in the manufacturing firm in Enugu, also a unit increase in worker’s participation will lead to 0.579 increase in employees turnover rate. Hence, since sig ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) is less than the 0.05 alpha, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that worker’s participation in decision-making have significant effect on the employees turnover rate in the manufacturing firm in Enugu.

4.2.2 Hypothesis two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between collective bargaining and employee retention in manufacturing firms in Enugu state. The result of correlation coefficient (r) statistic is summarized and presented in Table 4.9

Table 4.9: Test of hypothesis two

		Collective Bargaining	Employee retention
Collective	Pearson Correlation	1	0.279**
Bargaining	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.006

	N	95	95
Employee retention	Pearson Correlation	0.279**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.006	
	N	95	95

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlation estimate to test hypothesis two which state that there is no significant relationship between collective bargaining and employee retention in manufacturing firms in Enugu state is summarized and presented in Table 4.11 above. The value of the pearson correlation analysis between collective bargaining and employee retention was 0.279**. This signifies that collective bargaining predicted about 27.9% of employee retention. Therefore, there is a positive relationship between collective bargaining predicted and employee retention. This shows that increase in collective bargaining predicted, increases employee retention and vice versa. Hence, since sig ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) is less than the 0.05 alpha, the null hypothesis was rejected. We, therefore, conclude that there is a relationship between collective bargaining and employee retention in manufacturing firms in Enugu state.

4.3 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

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The study examined the effect of industrial democracy practices on employees performance, a case study of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. Specifically the study ascertained the effect of workers participation in decision making on employee turnover rate in the manufacturing firms in Enugu and determined the effect of collective bargaining on employee retention in the manufacturing firms in Enugu.. The study employed both primary and secondary data in achieving its objectives. The sample size of the study is 120 which was determined using Taro Yamane's formula. A total of 120 Questionnaires were administered to 120 respondents and 95 were received back, representing 79.17% response rate. The study found that

- i. The clustered mean on effect of workers participation in decision making on employee turnover rate in the manufacturing firms in Enugu was 3.43 which was accepted, this therefore implies that workers participation in decision making has effect on employee turnover rate in the manufacturing firms in Enugu..
- ii. Collective bargaining has effect on employee retention in the manufacturing firms in Enugu with clustered mean of 3.49 which was accepted.

The hypotheses tested show that

- i. Worker's participation in decision-making have a significant effect on the employees turnover rate in the manufacturing firm in Enugu $t = 6.831^{***}$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$)
- ii. There is a significant relationship between collective bargaining and employee retention in manufacturing firms in Enugu state ($r = 0.279^{**}$; $p = 0.000 < 0.05$).

5.0 CONCLUSION

This paper examined effect of industrial democracy practices on employees' performance, a case study of manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria. Industrial democracy is about democracy in the workplace between the management and the employees, where they both make decisions on all the issues pertaining to the organization, labour and management relations. In a situation where democracy is not given its pride of place in the running of an organization, conflicts and industrial unrest normally characterise such workplaces as the managed and the management seem to always be suspicious of each other and job satisfaction and efficient performance suffer. Basically, empirical results from this study finding indicate that industrial democracy practices has significant effect of on employees' performance. It was, therefore, deduced that worker's participation in decision-making have a significant effect on the employees turn over rate in the manufacturing firm in Enugu, there is a significant relationship between collective bargaining and employee retention in manufacturing firms in Enugu state,

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